

CHESS TEACHING PROCESS AND ITS LOGICAL THINKING OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Annotation: *Chess is considered a type of education that develops logical thinking and intellectual abilities. Moreover, it is a pedagogical process that develops psychological processes and is aimed at a person's mental, creative and educational maturity.*

Key words: *perseverance, diligence, communication, perception, attention, imagination, memory, thinking and volition*

The Presidential Decree "On measures to further develop and popularize chess and improve the system of training chess players" was adopted on the 14th of January in 2021 .

Based on this decision, the practice of organizing chess training for students of 150 general secondary schools on an experimental basis was expanded, and an additional 150 schools (including, 10 schools in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and in each region (except Tashkent region) , 15 schools in Tashkent region and Tashkent city) specialize in chess; 2, 3 and 4 grade students will be taught chess in the framework of the "Physical Education" subject in 1,000 secondary schools, based on an 18-hour plan, and methodical support will be provided to them. In addition, 2nd, 3rd and 4th graders of all other schools were assigned chess training within the "Physical Education" discipline.

Chess is considered a type of education that develops general and intellectual abilities, it is a pedagogical process that develops psychological processes and is aimed at a person's mental, creative and educational maturity. Chess serves as an additional educational tool in educating students to become more mature.

The teaching of the chess training course is related to mathematics, psychology, pedagogy and physical education and serves as the main factor in mastering these subjects.

Based on this curriculum, an annual calendar-plan is developed and approved by the deputy director of educational affairs of educational institutions. When making a calendar, it is necessary to take into account the correct distribution of intermediate and final control work, and when planning theoretical and practical training, climatic changes and the internal capacity of the school should be considered. In particular, when drawing up a thematic plan, the calendar should not exceed the total number of

hours allocated to the chapters (assigned to the subjects) in the curriculum, and should be distributed taking into account the level of mastery of the students.

The educational program contains the requirements for the results of the students' educational activities. It determines the action strategy of pedagogues at the beginning of the academic year. This curriculum is put into practice based on the periodic publication of textbooks.

Fundamental changes are taking place in primary education, the educational task of development is given priority. It helps to form the personality of junior high school students and fully reveal their creative abilities.

The correct organization of the process of teaching children the basics of chess allows us to make learning interesting, gives children opportunity to learn without forcing, keeps a constant interest in knowledge and uses different forms of learning. The main essence of the lessons is activities related to students' observation, comparison, classification, grouping, drawing conclusions, and finding patterns.

The game of chess in primary education opens wide opportunities for working in additional lessons, raises it to a new level of quality, and it has a positive effect on many mental processes in children, such as perception, attention, imagination, memory, thinking, and also on the development of such qualities as the initial forms of controlling voluntary behavior.

Learning to play chess from a young age helps many children in their development to open the door to creativity with their peers, especially thousands of non-communicative children living in rural areas and studying in rural high schools. Opportunities to expand the range of communication, full self-expression, and self-awareness allow these children to overcome isolation and imaginary shortcomings.

The game of chess develops thinking, helps the emergence of logical thinking, develops perseverance and diligence. A child who learns this game becomes more focused, self-critical, able to think independently, make decisions, fight to the end, and is not discouraged by failures. It has been experimentally confirmed that children who are attracted to the world of magical chess do better at school. Chess also has a positive effect on the improvement of many mental processes in children, such as intuition, attention, imagination, memory, thinking and early forms of control of voluntary behavior.

Alyokhin wrote: "Chess is not only knowledge and logic, but also deep imagination. I improved my character through chess. Chess is not only an example of life, but also an example of creativity. Chess, first of all, teaches to be objective. You can become a great chess master only by realizing your mistakes and shortcomings. Just as in life "(1924) [1] .

Chess games develop such an important set of qualities that they have long had a special social value, and it is one of the best and most interesting forms of recreation discovered by mankind. Therefore, the relevance of this article is , due to many factors,

meeting the needs of mental activity in active forms, and meaningful organization of students' free time.

Life forces us to ensure the correctness of our views at every step, to act decisively, to exercise restraint, determination, prudence and courage, the ability to imagine and subjugate imagination depending on the situation. And all this is what is required in chess. They are versatile and have a great emotional potential, they give "joy in the fight", but at the same time, they require the ability to attract attention and focus, appreciate time, endurance, recognize lies and truth, criticize not only the opponent, but also himself.

Chess is a wonderful school of creativity for children, it is a unique means of developing their creative thinking.

Chess is a way out of despair, loneliness, active recreation, satisfaction of interest in communication and self-expression. As José Raúl Capablanca said: "Chess is not just a game. It is an intellectual game with certain artistic features and many scientific elements. For mental work, chess means the same thing as sport for physical development, it is a pleasant way to develop physical exercise and certain characteristics of human nature ... "[2] .

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI:

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[1] Alexine, shaxmat bo'yicha 4-Jahon chempioni, "Oliy shaxmat yutuqlari yo'lida", -Minsk.

[2] Xose Raul Kapablanka - (1888-1942), kubalik shaxmatchi, shaxmat yozuvchisi, diplomat. Shaxmat bo'yicha 3-jahon chempioni (1921-1927), 1910-1930 yillarda dunyoning eng kuchli shaxmatchilaridan biri, ko'plab xalqaro turnirlarning g'olibi. "Mening shaxmat kareram" (rus tilidagi tarjimasi 1924 y.), " Shaxmat bo'yicha so'nggi ma'ruzalar "

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[2] Jose Raul Capablanca - (1888-1942), Cuban chess player, chess writer, diplomat. 3rd world chess champion (1921-1927), one of the strongest chess players in the world in 1910-1930, winner of many international tournaments. "My Chess Career" (Russian translation 1924), "Last Lectures on Chess"

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